

Table 2. Fungicides not effective against rice red stripe disease.^a CLRR1, Omon, Haugiang, summer-autumn 1990.

Chemical	Dosage (parts/thousand)	Time of application	Disease severity		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
			% leaves with disease at 7 DAS	% leaf area covered by disease at 14 DAS		
Kitazin 50 % EC	2	7 DAH	23.23	23.85	38.1	4.4
Hinosan 40 % EC	2.0	7 DAH	22.77	50.07	38.5	4.9
Kasuran 20 % WP	1.5	7 DAH	26.68	51.47	48.4	4.1
Oryzemat 8 % G	4 kg ai/ha	20 DBH	25.78	52.13	33.3	4.6
Control (unsprayed)	-	-	23.36	61.17	41.3	4.4
LSD (0.05)			ns	19.52	ns	ns

^a DAH = days after heading, DAS = days after spraying, DBH = days before heading.

Integrated pest management—insects

A parasitoid of stalk-eyed fly eggs in West Africa

R. C. Joshi, *International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria*; A. Polaszek, *International Institute of Entomology, London, U.K.*; V. C. Ofori, *National Youth Service Corps, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria*; and M. N. Ukwungwu, *National Cereals Research Institute, Badeggi, Nigeria*

During ecological investigations on the stalk-eyed fly (SEF) *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart, in 1989 wet season at IITA in southwestern Nigeria, we introduced SEF eggs into an experimental field to explore indigenous parasitoids.

Potted plants of rice cultivar Suakoko 8 carrying 1-d-old eggs from a screenhouse culture of SEF were exposed for 1 d in ricefields each week for 2 mo. Exposed

eggs were incubated in the laboratory in glass vials with a wet wad of cotton.

Three to four trichogrammatid wasps developed from each SEF egg. Upon dissection, each SEF egg showed as many as 8-9 larval/pupal stages of the parasitoids. Superparasitism was 12-15%. The developmental period of the parasitoid was 7-9 d.

The parasitoid was identified as *Trichogramma* sp. near *kalkae* Schulten & Feijen. This species has the distinctive genitalia characteristic of *T. kalkae*, a species found in SEF eggs in Malawi. However, the antennae of *T. sp.* near *kalkae* resemble those of *T. mandelai* Pintureau & Babault, found in eggs of Noctuidae (Lepidoptera) from Chad.

It may be that *T. sp.* near *kalkae* has not yet been described, or that the degree of intraspecific variation in genitalia characters or antennae is great. □

A population of brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes 1 and 2 mixture in Guangdong, China

Zhang Yang, Tan Yujuan, and Pan Ying, *Plant Protection Research Institute, Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Shih Pai, Guangzhou, China*

Guangdong in South China is the primary area of BPH immigration from Southeast Asia. BPH biotypes 2 and 3 are already present in the Philippines, Indonesia,

Vietnam, and the Solomon Islands. In June 1990, we collected a BPH colony in Gaozhou county, Guangdong, and isolated BPH biotypes 2 and 3.

For biotype evaluation, progenies of these BPH were evaluated using seedling bulk and survival rate tests. IR26 and Mudgo with the *Bph 1* resistance gene, IR36 and ASD7 with *bph 2*, IR56 with *Bph 3*, and TN1 with no resistance gene were used as identifying varieties.

Gravid BPH females were caged on 35-d-old plants of IR26, Mudgo, and ASD7, with 20 replications. First-

generation nymphs were evaluated on IR26, Mudgo, ASD7, and TN1 in the seedling bulk test. If some of the progenies damaged IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7 seedlings, the insects were mass-reared on TN1 for seedling bulk and survival rate tests.

In the seedling bulk tests, each 7-d-old rice seedling in the mass seedbox was infested with 10 newly hatched nymphs. When TN1 seedlings died, responses of all varieties were rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*. In survival rate tests, 10 third- to fourth-instar nymphs were caged on 35-d-old potted rice plants, with five replications per variety. BPH were counted 10 d after infestation.

Two and one replications of nymphs isolated with IR26 and Mudgo damaged IR26 and Mudgo seedlings, respectively. However, nymphs isolated with ASD7 did not damage IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7.

A progeny from a female isolated on

Damage rating

1. Damage rating to rice varieties infested with Gaozhou BPH colony and SC26 BPH population.

Survival (%)

2. Survival rate of SC26 BPH population. Bars with a common letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test (P 0.05).